

Debriefing (control group)

Welcome to the activity on elicitation of context-aware features. This is a controlled experiment and the participation is anonymous.

There are 4 questions in this survey.

Debriefing

Please answer the following questions about the experiment execution. *

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
My task in this experiment was clearly explained.	☐				
The time I received to perform my task was adequate.	☐				
My task in this experiment was easy.	☐				

Did you know the app "DorfFunk" before the experiment? *

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose only one of the following:

- No
- Yes, but I never used it.
- Yes, and I am (or was) a user of it.
- Yes, and I participate (or participated) in the app development team.
- Other

FINAL

Do you have any further comments about the experiment?

Please write your answer here:

Would you like to see the other side?

- In this experiment, some participants received an additional artifact to support their activity.
- Their artifact was a data-driven context model, which was created automatically based on the application data.
- The process that generates the artifact aims at identifying relevant contexts for given user tasks, with the purpose of supporting requirements engineers on the elicitation of context-aware functionalities.
- If you are interested in knowing how the data-driven context model looks like, you can download the PDF with information [REDACTED].

Please press **SUBMIT** to complete your participation.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Your is

Thank you for your participation!

IMPORTANT Please keep your experience today confidential.

This experiment will be repeated soon with other people and they should not know the details in advance.

If you want to know more about this activity, and would like to see the results, please send a e-mail to rodrigo.falcao@iese.fraunhofer.de with the subject "C5.2 Feedback"

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IESE Survey - Debriefing (control group)

Submit your survey.

Thank you for completing this survey.